

Assimineea eliae Paladilhe, 1875 (Gastropoda: Truncatelloidea), a valid species from the Atlantic coast of Europe

Assimineea eliae Paladilhe, 1875 (Gastropoda: Truncatelloidea), una especie válida de la costa atlántica de Europa

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ABSTRACT

Populations of the genus *Assimineea* were sampled in several sites of the French Atlantic coast in the estuaries of the Loire, Gironde and Adour, and in the Arcachon Basin. Shell morphology is homogeneous but examination of the radulae allows clear discrimination of two species, one identified as *A. grayana* Fleming, 1828 present at several sites from the Loire to the Arcachon basin, characterized by the presence of basal denticles on the rachidian tooth of the radula, and another, identified as *A. eliae* Paladilhe, 1875, lacking this feature and found in the Adour estuary. Syntypes of *A. eliae* were examined and it is concluded that this is an earlier name for *A. glaubrechti* van Aartsen, 2008, considered a junior synonym.

RESUMEN

Se muestrearon poblaciones del género *Assimineea* en varias localidades de la costa atlántica francesa, en los estuarios del Loira, Gironde y Adour, y en la cuenca de Arcachon. La morfología de las conchas es homogénea, pero el examen de las rádulas permite distinguir claramente dos especies: una identificada como *A. grayana* Fleming, 1828, presente en varias localidades desde el Loira hasta Arcachon, caracterizada por la presencia de denticulos basales en el diente raquídeo de la rádula; y otra, identificada como *A. eliae* Paladilhe, 1875, que carece de ellos y se encontró en el estuario del Adour. Se examinaron los sintipos de *A. eliae* y se concluye que se trata de un nombre anterior para *A. glaubrechti* van Aartsen, 2008, considerada una sinonimia posterior.

KEY WORDS: *Assimineea eliae*, *Assimineea grayana*, French Atlantic coast.

PALABRAS CLAVE: *Assimineea eliae*, *Assimineea grayana*, costa atlántica francesa.

INTRODUCTION

The mollusc family Assimineidae is a group of small gastropods found in coastal marine, brackish, freshwater and even terrestrial environment. They are represented along most temperate and

tropical coasts with their main centre of diversity in the western Pacific Ocean. Their taxonomy is difficult, in part because of their rather featureless shells on which early species descriptions

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Figure 1. The original figure of *Assimineae eliae* in PALADILHE (1875: pl. 21)
 Figura 1. Figura original de *Assimineae eliae* en PALADILHE (1875: lám. 21)

were based. The representatives of the family in European waters were revised by VAN AARTSEN (2008) who recognized five valid species of *Assimineae*, of which four described as new (*A. avilai* van Aartsen, 2008 from the Azores, *A. rolani* van Aartsen, 2008 from Madeira, *A. gittenbergeri* van Aartsen, 2008 from Tunisia, *A. glaubrechtii* van Aartsen, 2008 and *A. grayana* Fleming, 1828 from western Europe) and two valid species of *Paludinella* (*P. globularis* (Hanley, 1844) and *P. sicana* (Brugnone, 1876)). Rolán (2013) added *Assimineae moroccoensis* Rolán, 2013 and several more species from tropical West Africa.

ABBOTT (1958) suspected that *A. grayana* might have been introduced to England from the Far East between the XVth and the XVIIth centuries, arguing that it has an unusually limited distribution in the English Channel and North Sea, has no immediate relatives in North America or the Mediterranean but is remarkably similar to *A. violacea* Heude, 1882 from the east coast of China, and was first discovered in the Thames River i.e. a harbour area. However, this exotic origin has been doubted by FALKNER ET AL. (2002).

Assimineae eliae Paladilhe, 1875 was described from the French Atlantic coast, based on material from around La Rochelle collected by M. T. Letourneux, and material from Bayonne collected by L. de Folin and F. Bérillon. This name

was accepted as valid by FALKNER ET AL. (2002) but treated as a *nomen dubium* by VAN AARTSEN (2008) who instead described *Assimineae glaubrechtii* as new species based on material in MZB, Berlin from one of Paladilhe's localities (Bayonne). FALKNER ET AL. (2002) qualified *A. eliae* as a little-known species, partly confused with *A. grayana*, with a wide distribution along the Atlantic coast from La Rochelle south to Tangier (Morocco). The description was actually quite thorough according to standards of Paladilhe's time, and completed with a figure (here reproduced in Figure 1).

In agreement with VAN AARTSEN'S (2008) treatment, *Assimineae glaubrechtii* was reported from Gafanha do Areão, Beira Litoral, Portugal by HOLYOAK & HOLYOAK (2013) who provided a detailed account of habitat, external morphology and the radula. This supports the occurrence in Portugal reported in the original description of *A. eliae*, regarding which ROLÁN (2013) suspected a misidentification of a freshwater species. Alternatively, from PALADILHE'S (1875: 6) wording ("en 1873 un de nos correspondants nous expédiait de Coïmbre (Portugal) la même coquille..."), it could be understood that Coimbra was the place of residence of whoever sent the shells, not the actual collecting site.

Here we report on several populations of *Assimineae* observed along the French Atlantic coast, including one

(Bayonne) of Paladilhe's original localities, demonstrate that two similar but not closely related species are present, and propose to restore the name *A. eliae* for that one later described as *A. glau-brechti*.

Radular characters have been found useful to discriminate species among this group with rather featureless shells. The type species *A. grayana* is described by THIELE (1927: 115) and BANDEL (1984: 25-26, fig. 39) as having a short, stout central (rachidian) tooth provided with three denticles on each side of the basal part. THIELE (1927: 126) used a "Sectio" [*Eussoia* Preston, 1912] for species of *Assiminea* where the basal denticles are absent. Fukuda & Ponder (2003: 2014 – 2032) also used the presence or absence of the basal denticles to discriminate between groups (subfamilies) in the Assimineidae: Group 1 with basal cusps and group 2 without them.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Specimens of *Assiminea* were collected in eight locations along the French Atlantic coast: from north to south, one in Morbihan, three in the Loire estuary, one in Gironde estuary, two in Arcachon basin and one in Bayonne (with two sampling events). Type specimens of the Paladilhe collection are known to be housed at University of Montpellier

(BREURE & AUDIBERT, 2017), therefore we enquired there about syntypes of *Assiminea eliae*.

Photographs were taken of living specimens using a Nikon DS-2MV mounted on a Nikon SMZ1000 stereomicroscope. Still images of shells were captured using a Nikon DXM 1200F camera mounted on the same stereomicroscope, taking a series of views focused on distinct planes which were assembled using CombineZ stacking software (HADLEY, 2006). Protoconchs and radula were imaged using a JEOL SM 6490LV scanning electron microscope at University of Málaga. For this, specimens were dried, mounted on conductive copper tape, and coated for SEM observation. Radulae were extracted from a whole specimen, first dissolving the shell in acid and soaking the soft parts in concentrated KOH, then cleaned and mounted on a stub for examination under the scanning electron microscope.

RESULTS

The examined lots were morphologically quite homogeneous and seemed at first sight to be all conspecific, but examination of the radulae revealed that two unrelated species were present. The detail of material examined and diagnostic characters are given below.

Assiminea grayana Fleming, 1828 (Figs. 2A-I, 3, 4A, B, 5A, B)

Material examined – FRANCE • 24 spm (dry; Fig. 2A-C, 5 A, B); left bank of la Loire, Paimboeuf, Le Petit Carnet; 17 Feb. 2008; J.L. Deleamarre leg.; mud covered with leaves among reeds • 7 spm. (dry, largest of all), left bank of la Loire, East of Grand Carnet near channel entrance, among reeds; 10 Aug. 2008; J.L. Deleamarre, leg. • 24 spm. (ethanol preserved, Fig. 4A, B, operculum MEB 4790), right bank of la Loire, Lavau-sur-Loire; 27 Feb. 2016; J.L. Deleamarre leg.; on launching slipway • 12 spm. (10 ethanol-preserved, Fig. 2D-F); Bordeaux[x], right bank; Apr. 2008; L. Charles leg. • 14 spm.; Morbihan, la Vilaine, left bank, downstream Arzal dam; May 2009; J.L. Deleamarre, leg.; among reeds • 14 spm. (Fig. 2G-I); Arcachon Basin, Le Port des Tuiles; 06 Jan. 2009; J. L. Deleamarre leg. • 16 spm. (ethanol-preserved, mostly juvenile); Arcachon Basin, Port d'Audenge; 06 Jan. 2009; J. L. Deleamarre leg.

The shells (Fig. 2A-F) are similar to those found further north along the coasts of the North Sea and English

Channel, and need not to be described anew. The identification was confirmed by the characters of the radula (Fig. 4A,

Figure 2. Shells of *Assimineina*. A-C: *A. grayana* from Paimboeuf, Le Petit Carnet, 17 Feb. 2008 (height 3.9 mm); D-F: *A. grayana* from Bordeaux, April 2008 (height 4.8 mm); G-I: *A. grayana* from Arcachon Basin, le Port des Tuiles, 06 Jan. 2009 (height 2.8 mm); J-L: *A. eliae* from Bayonne, left bank of the Adour, 20 Apr. 2025 (height 3.5 mm).

Figure 3. A, B: living specimens of *Assimineina grayana* from Corsept, near Pamboeuf.

Figura 2. Conchas de *Assimineina*. A-C: *A. grayana* de Paimboeuf, Le Petit Carnet, 17 feb. 2008 (altura: 3,9 mm); D-F: *A. grayana* de Burdeos, abril de 2008 (altura: 4,8 mm); G-I: *A. grayana* de la cuenca de Arcachon, Port des Teiles, 6 ene. 2009 (altura: 2,8 mm); J-I: *A. eliae* de Bayona, margen izquierda del Adour, 20 abr. 2025 (altura: 3,5 mm).

Figura 3. A, B: ejemplares vivos de *Assimineina grayana* de Corsept, cerca de Pamboeuf.

B), which is about 130 μm in a specimen ca. 3 mm high. Each row comprises a stout central (=rachidian) tooth, flanked by a pair of lateral and two pairs of marginal teeth. The central tooth is about 20 μm broad, with five terminal cusps sharply decreasing in size from center to sides, and three strong denticles on each side of the basal part of the tooth. Lateral teeth have an elongate stalk

giving them a spoon-like shape, with terminal cusps similar to those of the central tooth. The inner marginals resemble the laterals except in having fewer (only 3-4) cusps, whereas the outer marginals terminate in a row of 10-12 minute, closely set cusps.

The protoconch (Fig. 5A, B) comprises about two whorls, with distinct protoconch 1 (embryonic shell) and proto-

Figure 4. A: Partial view of the radula of a specimen of *A. grayana* from Lavau-sur-Loire. B: Closeup of central and lateral teeth, showing the basal denticles on the central tooth. C: Partial view of the radula of a specimen of *A. eliae* from Bayonne. D: closeup of central, lateral teeth and inner marginals of another specimen, showing the absence of basal denticles on the central tooth. Abbreviations, ce: central (=rachidian) tooth; la: lateral teeth; m¹: inner marginal teeth; m²: outer marginal teeth. *Figura 4. A: Vista parcial de la rádula de un ejemplar de A. grayana de Lavau-sur-Loire. B: Vista aumentada de los dientes centrales y laterales, mostrando los denticulos basales del diente central. C: Vista parcial de la rádula de un ejemplar de A. eliae de Bayona. D: Vista aumentada de los dientes centrales, laterales y marginales internos de otro ejemplar, mostrando la ausencia de denticulos basales en el diente central. Abreviaturas, ce: diente central (=raquídeo); la: dientes laterales; m¹: dientes marginales internos; m²: dientes marginales externos.*

conch 2. Protoconch 1 is about $\frac{3}{4}$ of a whorl, measures ca. 150 µm in maximum diameter, is ornamented with an irregular honeycomb-like microsculpture, and is clearly delimited by a slightly raised edge. Protoconch 2 is about 360 µm in maximum diameter,

comprises $\frac{1}{4}$ whorl with a distinct microsculpture of ca. 12 spiral threads, much narrower than their interspaces, and is clearly demarcated from the smooth teleoconch. This pattern denotes a planktotrophic larval development for this species.

Assimineea eliae Paladilhe, 1875 (Figs. 2J-L, 4C, D, 5C, D, 7)

Material examined – FRANCE • 5 spm (syntypes, Fig. 7); Bayonne; before Oct. 1874; F. Bérillon leg.; University of Montpellier • 12 spm. (dry, Fig. 2J-L); Bayonne, left bank of river Adour; Apr. 2008; J.L. Delemarre leg.; among reeds • 26 spm. (Fig. 4C, D); Bayonne, left bank of Adour, downstream motorway bridge; 20 Apr. 2025; J.L. Delemarre leg.; among reeds; MNHN.

Figure 5. A: Protoconch of *Assimineea grayana*, specimen from Paimboeuf, Le Petit Carnet. B: detail of the embryonic shell (protoconch 1) showing honeycomb sculpture. C: protoconch of *A. eliae*, specimen from Bayonne. D: protoconch of *A. eliae*, specimen from Beira Litoral, Portugal (reproduced from HOLYOAK & HOLYOAK, 2013).

Figura 5. A: Protoconcha de *Assimineea grayana*, ejemplar de Paimboeuf, Le Petit Carnet. B: detalle de la concha embrionaria (protoconcha 1) que muestra la escultura alveolada. C: protoconcha de *A. eliae*, ejemplar de Bayona. D: protoconcha de *A. eliae*, ejemplar de Beira Litoral, Portugal (reproducido de HOLYOAK & HOLYOAK, 2013).

The shells (Fig. 7) are essentially similar to those of *A. grayana*. The only morphological character we found to be discriminant is that of the radula (Fig. 3 C, D), in which the central (=rachidian) tooth is less sturdy (no more than 15 µm broad) and lacks the clusters of basal denticles on the stalk. We could not see essential differences in the lateral and marginal teeth.

The protoconch is also of a multispiral type, being about 300 µm in

maximum diameter, but we could not distinguish any spiral sculpture. Nevertheless, this may be due to the erosion of the apical area which affects all of our specimens from Bayonne. The specimen from Portugal illustrated by HOLYOAK & HOLYOAK (2013) seems less eroded and the protoconch 1 appears clearly demarcated from protoconch 2, but the latter has only a hint of elongate granules along spiral lines, not definite threads as in *A. grayana*.

Figure 6. The habitat of *Assiminea grayana* near Paimboeuf. A, B: general views of the habitat on the south bank of the Loire, with reed stands (“roselières”) along the bank. C, D: occurrence of *Assiminea grayana* among reed roots or on the barren mud.

Figura 6. Hábitat de *Assiminea grayana* cerca de Paimboeuf. A, B: vistas generales del hábitat en la orilla sur del Loira, con juncales (“roselières”) a lo largo de la orilla. C, D: presencia de *Assiminea grayana* entre raíces de juncos o en el lodo despejado.

DISCUSSION

Our material documents *Assiminea grayana* as a well-established species on the French Atlantic coast from the Loire estuary to Arcachon Basin, where its occurrence was questioned by FALKNER *ET AL.* (2002: 92). This represents a noteworthy secular progression, since the species was not reported from anywhere in France at the time of GERMAIN (1931: “Elle ne vit pas en France, mais elle a été signalée en Belgique par F. de Malzine [1867] sur la plage près de la frontière française.”). It was found in the Seine estuary only since the 1960s (FALKNER *ET AL.*, 2002). To the North, *A. grayana* has expanded its range in recent decades to include coasts of the Irish Sea in north-west England and south-west Scotland, and of the Atlantic on the coast of south-west Ireland in the River

Shannon estuary (NATIONAL BIODIVERSITY NETWORK, 2025), and its invasive behaviour supports ABBOT’s (1951) view that the species is not native of Europe.

Assiminea eliae was reported from Ria de Arousa, Spain by FALKNER *ET AL.* (2002) (based on specimens misidentified as *A. grayana* in CADÉE (1968), which they examined) also and from Tangiers, Morocco (based on a specimen in MNHN, leg. Gofas 1971). FALKNER *ET AL.* (2002) suggested that *Assiminea recta* Mousson, 1874, described from a river mouth at Rabat, Morocco, should be investigated as a possible earlier name for *A. eliae*. This was however rebutted by VAN AARTSEN (2008) who considered it as a probable synonym of *Peringia ulvae* Pennant, 1777, a conclusion which is supported with the syntype illustrated in NEUBERT *ET AL.* (2023: pl. 10 fig. 11). There is a report of *A. eliae* from

Figure 7. Syntypes of *Assiminea eliae* in University of Montpellier. A: original label. B: five syntypes. C, D: detailed views of syntypes 1 (height 3.4 mm) and 4 (height 2.2 mm). Photographs courtesy of Suzanne Jiquel (Université de Montpellier).

Figura 7. Sintipos de *Assiminea eliae* en la Universidad de Montpellier. A: etiqueta original. B: cinco sintipos. C, D: vistas detalladas de los sintipos 1 (altura 3,4 mm) y 4 (altura 2,2 mm). Fotografías cortesía de Suzanne Jiquel (Universidad de Montpellier).

Arcachon Basin by AMANIEU (1969) but occurrence beneath stones and co-occurrence with *Ovatella bidentata* (p. 516) suggest those were *Paludinella* spp.

Assiminea eliae resembles *Assiminea grayana* to the point that MONTEROSATO (1906: 128) considered it as a probable synonym. It is only through the characters of the radula (with three basal denticles on each side of the central tooth in *grayana*, and specimens from the Loire estuary, without them in specimens from Bayonne reported by THIELE (1927: 118) and on specimens from Portugal identified as *A. glaubrechtii* by HOLYOAK & HOLYOAK (2013). This is of utmost

importance in the systematics of assimi-neids (THIELE, 1927; FUKUDA & PONDER, 2003).

Comparing the specimens collected by us at Bayonne with the original description and with the syntypes in the Paladilhe collection, we can see no reason not to adopt the name *Assiminea eliae* for this species. It does not qualify as *nomen oblitum* because it has been used as valid after 1899 (e.g. GERMAIN, 1931: 594-595) and anyway there was no alternative name used more than 25 times (ICZN Art. 23.9).

Furthermore, we consider *Assiminea glaubrechtii*, based on material from one

Figure 8. The habitat of *Assiminea eliae* near Bayonne. A: general view of the habitat on the south bank of the Adour, with reed stands. B: detail of the collecting site.

Figura 8. Hábitat de Assiminea eliae cerca de Bayona. A: vista general del hábitat en la orilla sur del Adour, con juncales. B: detalle del sitio de recolección.

of Paladilhe's localities (Bayonne), as a junior synonym. The holotype (ZMB Moll. 111490) and five paratypes (ZMB Moll. 111490) of the latter species are in Museum für Naturkunde (Berlin) in the collection of Friedrich Paetel where all the original labels were removed at some time (pers. comm. Thomas von Rintelen, Museum für Naturkunde). These specimens were in Paetel's collection before 1888 (PAETEL, 1888: 472) and at that time the most likely collector around Bayonne was Bérillon, either directly or possibly through Paladilhe in which case those specimens would have been also syntypes of *A. eliae*, were they still documented by original labels.

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